

EVALUATION OF GROUND-BASED SURFACE SOLAR RADIATION DATA VERSUS SATELLITE PRODUCTS (CASE STUDY: IRAN)

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Abstract

Surface solar radiation (SSR) is one of the key parameters in climate and agricultural studies and is an important component of land-surface energy models. Due to limitations in ground-based measurements, SSR is currently estimated by various empirical radiation methods which are solely valid for specific climates and locations. This work is aimed to evaluate SSR, derived from three satellite-based radiation products over Iran from 2012 to 2015 on a daily basis. The satellite products have been developed by Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System (CERES) and two datasets of CLARA and SARA from Satellite Application Facility on Climate Monitoring (CM SAF). The results of validation of SSR estimation by all three products at all stations showed that, with slightly difference, all three products are able to estimate the SSR in Iran. However, SARA shows the highest performance ($R^2 = 0.93$ and a RMSE of 22.36 W/m^2) in comparison with CLARA ($R^2= 0.91$; RMSE= 24.39 W/m^2) and CERES ($R^2= 0.92$; RMSE= 25.23). Evaluation of satellite-based products in monthly and seasonal scales shows that satellite products underestimate the SSR in winter and spring. This bias is likely due to the increase in cloudiness and aerosol concentration induces in those seasons. It seems that due to the high accuracy of the aforementioned satellite products (especially SARA), it is possible to use these data in estimating SSR in places where the ground measurements are not available.

Keywords: *Surface solar radiation, Assessment, Satellite-based products, Iran.*

Introduction

Solar radiation controls the Earth's Climate and is a fundamental key variable in meteorological studies and in the management of agricultural systems. Surface solar radiation (SSR) is the radiation that received on a horizontal surface in spectral range of $0.29\text{-}2.8 \mu\text{m}$ and is an important input for many crop growth models and agrometeorological studies.

There are several methods to obtain SSR. The best way is the ground-based measurement with pyranometers (Ruiz-Arias *et al.*, 2015). These radiometers are sensitive and high quality sensors (Urraca *et al.*, 2017) which provide the best estimate of SSR (Yang *et al.*, 2018). However, because of the high cost of their installation and maintenance, they do not have suitable spatial coverage, especially in mountainous areas with complex terrain (Wang *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, due to the need for high spatial resolution and efforts to improve observational data, the use of satellite data in the estimation of SSR, such as the CERES and CM SAF products, was developed. Almorox *et al.* (2017) in Spain and Carmona *et al.* (2017) in Argentina evaluated the SSR estimated by CERES. The results showed a strong correlation between CERES and measured monthly radiation data with $R^2= 0.96$ in Spain and $R^2= 0.995$ in Argentina. These results are similar to the values provided by Chen *et al.* (2014) with an average of $R^2= 0.92$ for

worldwide distributed stations. Alexandri *et al.* (2017) compared the SSR estimated by satellite and reanalysis products in the Mediterranean region. The results showed that the monthly SARAH satellite product underestimates SSR in the study area with MABD= 11.9 W/m² and MBD= 7.1 W/m².

Despite the importance of estimating SSR in agricultural studies in Iran, there is not enough research in this topic in Iran. Sabziparvar and Shetaee (2007); Sabziparvar (2008), Gholamnia *et al.* (2015) and Javadi *et al.* (2017) investigated SSR using empirical models. Lotfinejad *et al.* (2018) and Khosravi *et al.* (2018) using some artificial intelligence methods in some stations of Iran that show highly accurate estimates. Noori *et al.* (2018) estimated SSR with the experimental models of Angstrom and Hargreaves-Samani, two of reanalysis models and satellite-based product (CM SAF) in Qazvin, and showed that the calibrated Angstrom model had the best performance compared to other products. Nevertheless, most of these studies tested their approaches for a small region of Iran.

Due to the need of improving the spatial and temporal resolution of SSR data and the absence of ground-based SSR data in some areas of Iran, Using the appropriate estimation method with high quality data is essential. Satellite models with high spatial and temporal resolution can be an appropriate alternative source for regions with heterogeneous stations and complex terrain. Of course, it should be noted that the use of any product as a substitute for measured data is along with the limitations. Therefore, these restrictions need to be reviewed.

The objective of the present paper is aimed to evaluate SSR, derived from three satellite-based radiation products (CERES, CLARA and SARAH) over Iran from 2012 to 2015 on a daily basis.

Material and Methods

Ground-based datasets

In this study, surface solar radiation extracted from 24 stations (Fig. 1) by Iran Meteorological Organization (IRIMO) from December 2012 to November 2015 to assess the CERES and CM SAF (SARAH and CLARA) surface solar radiation products. Each station contained a CM5 pyranometer manufactured by Kipp&Zonen, Holland, and a Campbell-Stokes recorder to measure the daily SSR (Moradi, 2009). Large parts of ground-based data errors are caused by technical failure of the pyranometers such as Cosine response, azimuth and temperature response and stability and operational errors such as problems of sensor, dust or dew on the equipment and station shot down (Younes *et al.* 2005). In this study, Moradi's proposed method was used to control the quality of measurement datasets (Moradi, 2009).

Satellite datasets

The satellite scientific instrument of CERES (Cloud and the Earth's Radiant Energy System) is a component of NASA's Earth Observation System (EOS). The CERES_SYN1deg_Ed4A product with spatial resolution of 1 degree and temporal resolution of daily is included surface solar radiation. Other products that investigate in this project, are CM SAF CLARA and SARAH. The Climate Monitoring Satellite Application Facility (CM SAF) is devoted to supplying high quality records for climate applications from geostationary and polar orbiting satellites, at the European and global scale (Sanchez-Lorenzo *et al.* 2013; Urraca *et al.* 2017) by the European Organization for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT). The CLARA product is based on observations of the AVHRR instruments on board the polar orbiting NOAA and METOP satellites. CLARA provides global information on SSR from 1982 to 2015 with a spatial resolution of 0.25 degree and temporal resolution of daily. The SARAH

product has a specific climate algorithm that can be applied to the geostationary Meteosat satellites (Meteosat-2 to Meteosat-7) and recovered climate variable with good quality. The same algorithm used for MVIRI is also applied to SEVIRI. This product was extracted daily means on a regular spaced raster with a spatial resolution of 0.05 degree of SSR (Buffat *et al.* 2015). SARAH is designed to study on Europe, Africa and eastern Atlantic and for this reason does not have any coverage on a part of north of the east of Iran (Mashhad station).

Methodology

Various products of solar radiation in this study, are in the form of a gridded data and in NetCDF format. So, to implement the comparison between ground-based observations with all of the products on the original grid scale, the nearest neighbourhood interpolation method was used to match the data stations with Climate Data Operator software (CDO). Then, measured SSR is validated with three satellite-based products by four metrics of determination coefficient (R^2), bias (MBD), mean absolute bias (MABD), relative mean absolute bias (RMABD) and root mean square error (RMSE).

Results and Discussion

Figure 2 represents comparison among various satellite products with daily measured SSR datasets taken from 24 stations from December 2012 to November 2015. The scatterplots show that SARAH has a higher accuracy than the other two products with $R^2= 0.93$, MBD= -0.1 W/m^2 , RSME= 22.4 W/m^2 and MABD= 15 W/m^2 . Comparison of MBD values between satellite products and observational SSR shows that CERES and CLARA with 4.68 and 1.26 W/m^2 , respectively tend to overestimate and SARAH with 0.1 W/m^2 tend to underestimate. Also, most MBD was obtained by CERES and lowest by SARAH. Wang *et al.* (2018) showed the SARAH-E with MBD= $7.5 \pm 1.9 \text{ W/m}^2$ has better performance than CLARA-A2 with MBD= $10 \pm 1.7 \text{ W/m}^2$ in the study of daily SSR in China. Also, Urraca *et al.* (2017) showed SARAH had the best estimate of SSR compared to several satellite products in Spain with lowest standard deviation and MAE= $1.10 \pm 0.13 \text{ MJ/m}^2$, MBE= $0.22 \pm 0.36 \text{ MJ/m}^2$.

The study of the mean monthly SSR derived from three satellite products (Fig. 3) shows the most MBD in CERES occurs in August and September with 10.3 and 10.6 W/m^2 , respectively and in CLARA and SARAH in Jun and September with 11.1 and 7.8 W/m^2 , respectively. Also, CERES display an underestimate in December to February and an overestimate in March to November by bias. An underestimate in November to May and overestimate in June to October was represent by CLARA and SARAH. In a study by Urraca *et al.* (2017), CLARA and SARAH in Europe in May and June showed underestimate and other months showed overestimate. Alexandri *et al.* (2017) showed the Cloud Fractional Cover (CFC) and Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) determine the difference between bias value in the two products of CERES and SARAH by survey the effective parameters on SSR.

The results of this study are similar to those presented by Urraca *et al.* (2017) and Sanchez-Lorenzo *et al.* (2013) that showed the minimum RMSE (MABD) in September to December (autumn and early winter) and the maximum RMSE (MABD) in April to June. The high magnitude of these two statistical indicators in the spring could be due to high insolation.

Investigating the spatial variations of MBD between measured SSR and satellite-based products showed that there was a tendency to underestimate at the stations with higher height (Shahrekord, Yasuj, Kerman and Hamedan). The Ahvaz station with high pollution and aerosol and two coastal stations of Gorgan and Bandar Abbas, which are less height than the other stations studied, showed the highest overestimate. In this way, Urraca *et al.* (2017) showed the

satellite products in region with high height and snow covered in winter tend to underestimate and regions surrounded by high aerosol and coastal areas tend to overestimate. Satellite imagery gridded in coastal areas with high humidity contain land and sea climate condition and this creates a lot of complications in accurate estimation of SSR in these areas (Thomas *et al.*, 2016; Urraca *et al.*, 2017; Urraca *et al.*, 2018). In other stations in Iran, satellite products provided an appropriate estimate for SSR.

Figure 1. Locations of the 24 ground stations used with their ID's in the present study in Iran.

Figure 2. Scatterplot of daily SSR derived from versus satellite products and ground-based datasets taken from 24 stations of Iran in the period from 2012 to 2015.

Figure 3. Mean monthly values of the MBD (W/m^2) obtained between observational and versus satellite-based product over Iran.

Conclusions

In this study, the SSR in Iran was compared to three satellite-based products (CERES, CLARA and SARAH). Based on the results, it can be concluded that all of these satellite products have a significantly reliable performance in estimating SSR in Iran. Also, it was seen that satellite products in the winter and spring tend to underestimate and the cause of the negative MBD values can be related to cloudy conditions.

Although satellite products are in error in atmospheric conditions with the presence of clouds, water vapour and dust storms, with high survey and recording these atmospheric phenomena, it is possible to obtain accurate estimates of surface radiation with higher precision. It can also be said that the effect of clouds on satellite products is greater than the effect of aerosols and water vapour (Urraca *et al.* 2018), because the cloudiness in the cold seasons affected the same way in all areas on derived SSR of these satellite-based products. Due to the high accuracy of satellite products in the central and eastern area of Iran, these products can be a good superseded to stations with high missing data or areas with lacking ground measurements.

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